

“The Reflective Approach. Ethnopsychological-Pedagogical Projections and Paradigms (Scientific Contributions in The Period 1990-2023)” Book Review

“The Reflective Approach. Ethnopsychological-Pedagogical Projections and Paradigms (Scientific Contributions in The Period 1990-2023)” Kitap İncelemesi

Koleva, I., M. Legurska, G. Bogomilova, G. Bogdenov, K. Angelov, D. Andreeva, P. Zarev, E. Vitanova, L. Kamenov, K. Angelov, M. Kurmanbekova. The reflective approach. Ethnopsychological-pedagogical projections and paradigms (scientific contributions in the period 1990-2023) (2024), Sofia, University publishing house, St. Kliment Ohridski

 Elena Vitanova¹

¹Phd. Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski", vitanova_64@abv.bg,(Sorumlu Yazar/ Corresponding author)

The collective monograph “The Reflective Approach. Ethnopsychological-pedagogical projections and paradigms (Scientific contributions in the period 1990-2023)” is the second volume of the series of monographs (Library „Ethnopsychology and Education, Koleva, I., 2008)¹. The idea for the compilation and structure of the monographic work belongs to Prof. Dr. Irina Koleva- one of the founders of the Bulgarian school of the reflective approach in the system of pedagogical interaction and a leading specialist in the field of ethnopsychology, ethnopedagogy, and intercultural education.

The monograph highlights the scientific contributions in theoretical and research/empirical terms of the Bulgarian school of the reflective approach. The reflective approach (now based on the competence-oriented educational policy) is established as a dominant approach in the European and Asian educational space. The emphasis is on values, understood as an activity and dispositional characteristic of the personality. All aspects of the personal and praxeological reflection are scientifically substantiated.

The monograph presents scientific research carried out in the field of a relatively new scientific field - ethnopsychological-pedagogy. The beginning of scientific research in this field was registered in the period 1986-1990 (Koleva, I., 1990, 1993)². Subsequently, the conceptual theses for understanding reflection and the reflective approach were developed and approved by many scientists- researchers at all stages of education - preschool, school, and higher.

The monograph contains ten studies by Bulgarian and Kazakh scientists from the Sofia University “St. Kliment Ohridski” (Bulgaria/ and Turan University- Kazakhstan)- representing the Bulgarian school of the reflective approach.

¹ Koleva, I. (2008). Ethnopsychological model of educational interaction. Sofia – first edition

² Koleva, I. (1993). Child- Teacher - Environment, S: Koleva, I. (1990). Socialization, Reflection, Situations, S.

In terms of empirical research, the monograph presents ethnopsychological ethnopedagogical models for the application of social, cultural, and educational technologies and practices using the reflexive approach. In this regard, it is intended for students and specialists working in mono- and intercultural educational environments.

In terms of theoretical research, the monograph is intended for students and doctoral candidates in the following specialties: “Ethnology and Cultural Anthropology”, “Pedagogy”, “Psychology”, “Social Activities”, “Sociology”, “Culturology”, “Social Pedagogy and Social Work” and all specialties whose curricula include courses in ethnopsychology, ethnopedagogy, intercultural education, pedagogical interaction in an intercultural educational environment, integration of minorities, early childhood development, andragogy, civic education and others concerning the ethno-psychological-pedagogical profile of ethnic communities and groups.

The leading study, authored by Prof. Dr. Irina Koleva, presents the methodological foundations of ethnopsychological-pedagogical paradigms and aspects of ethno-pedagogical projections. At the same time, theoretical and research/empirical contributions of the Bulgarian scientific reflexive school in the field of ethno-psychological-pedagogy are systematized, and the scientific innovation of a total of nine doctoral dissertations developed and successfully defended in the period 2013- 2023 is proven.

Each of the remaining nine studies reflects purposeful aspects of the dissertation research of these scientists, as well as the contributions of each of them to the system of preschool, school, and higher education. They are presented in two plans: theoretical and research/empirical. Each of the dissertation studies was carried out in the context of ethnopsychology and ethnopedagogy of educational interaction, in the field of intellectual, motivational, didactic, personal, cooperative, and communication reflection. They cover all addressees in the field of education: teachers, principals, school psychologists, parents, etc., including interested parties- local authorities, non-governmental organizations, etc.

There is a transfer of the Bulgarian school to the Asian research educational space (R. Kazakhstan, Kazakh National Pedagogical University – “Abaya”, M. Kurmanbekova, 2022)³.

Основните иновации са по посока на:

The main innovations are in the direction of:

Reflective pedagogical technology on the rights of the child – Mirena Legurska;

- Pedagogical technology of entertainment in an interethnic environment in the conditions of kindergarten - Galina Bogomilova;
- Ethnopsychological aspects of the socio-educational functions of Facebook in our country – Georgi Bogdanov;
- Ethnopsychological model of a reflective picture for teacher qualification – Anelia Andreeva;
- Teacher’s reflective model for sociocultural competence – Petar Zarev;
- Contemporary intercultural educational programs for ethnographic and historical museums in Bulgaria- Elena Vitanova;
- A reflective picture of discriminatory factors in the field of secondary education (2012-2017) – Lalo

³ <https://kaznpu.kz/ru/>

Kamenov;

- Ethnopsychological model of coordination-education policies in Bulgaria (1989-2019) –Kaloyan Angelov;
- Preparation of a future teacher–psychologist for the involvement of adolescents in project research activities – Kurmanbekova Manshuk.

All reflective models of educational interaction have been tested and implemented in educational and administrative-management practice at the national and transnational levels.

References

1. Koleva, I. (2008). Ethnopsychological model of educational interaction. Sofia – first edition
2. Koleva, I. (1993). Child- Teacher - Environment, S: Koleva, I. (1990). Socialization, Reflection, Situations, S.
3. Koleva, I., M. Legurska, G. Bogomilova, G. Bogdenov, K. Angelov, D. Andreeva, P. Zarev, E. Vitanova, L. Kamenov, K. Angelov, M. Kurmanbekova. The reflective approach. Ethnopsychological-pedagogical projections and paradigms (scientific contributions in the period 1990-2023) (2024), Sofia, University publishing house, St. Kliment Ohridski
4. <https://kaznpu.kz/ru/>